

UMUM TA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA "ALGEBRAIK KASRLAR VA ULAR USTIDA AMALLAR" BOBINI O'QITISH METODIKASI

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O'zbekistonning iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy sohalarida yuqori natijalarga erishishi, jahon iqtisodiy tizimida to'laqonli sheriklik o'rnini egallay borishi, inson faoliyatining barcha jabhalarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan yuqori darajada foydalanishning ko'lamlari qanday bo'lishiga hamda bu texnologiyalar ijtimoiy mehnat samaradorligining oshishida qanday ahamiyat kasb etishiga bog'liq.

Ta'lim jarayonini, oliy ta'limning o'quv reja va dasturlarini yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar va o'qitish usullarini keng joriy etish, magistratura ilmiy ta'lim jarayonini sifat jihatdan yangilash va zamonaviy tashkiliy shakllarni joriy etish asosida yanada takomillashtirish;

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi farmonida ta'lim va ilm-fan sohalarini rivojlantirish borasida belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini ta'minlash hamda sohadagi dolzarb hujjatda ta'lim muassasalarining moddiy texnik bazasini mustahkamlash yangi ta'lim muassasalarini qurish, ta'mirlash va kapital ta'mirlash barobarida ularni zamonaviy o'quv va laboratoriya jihozlari, kompyuter texnikasi va o'quv metodik qo'llanmalar bilan ta'minlash nazarda tutilgan.

1-masala. Katerning turg'un suvdagi tezligi soatiga a km ga, daryo oqimining tezligi soatiga b km ga teng. Katerning daryo oqimi bo'yicha harakat tezligi uning daryo oqimiga qarshi harakat tezligidan necha marta ortiq?

Yechish: Katerning daryo oqimi bo'yicha tezligi soatiga $(a+b)$ km ga teng; Oqimga qarshi tezligi soatiga $(a-b)$ km ga teng. Shuning uchun daryo oqimi bo'yicha harakat tezligi oqimga qarshi harakat tezligidan

$$(a+b)/(a-b)$$

marta ortiq bo'ladi. Mana shu ifoda algebraik kasr deyiladi.

$$(a+b)/(a-b)$$

$a+b$ kasrni surati, $a-b$ kasrning maxraji.

Umuman, surat va maxraji algebraik ifodalar

bo'lgan kasr algebraik kasr deyiladi.

Masalan,

$$a/b, 3/(x+y), (x(b+c))/(y(a-c))$$

Agar algebraik kasrga kiruvchi harflar o'rniga biror sonlar qo'yilsa, u holda hisoblashlar bajarilganidan keyin shu algebraik kasrning son qiymati hosil bo'ladi. Masalan,

$a=10, b=8$ bo'lganida

$$(a+b)/(a-b)$$

algebraik kasrning son qiymati

$$(10+8)/(10-8)=18/2=9$$

ga teng bo'ladi

Kasrlarni qisqartirish uchun bu kasrlarning surat va maxrajini ularning umumiy ko'paytuvchisiga bo'lish kerak.

Agar a/b kasrning surat va maxrajidagi ishora qarama-qarshisiga o'zgartirilsa, u holda berilgan kasrga qarama-qarshi kasr hosil bo'ladi.

Masalan, $(-a)/(1-a) = -a/(1-a) = a/(a-1)$

Interfaol usullar yangi materialni yuqori sifatli o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi: - ijodiy xarakterdagi mashqlar; - guruh topshiriqlari; - tarbiyaviy, rolli, ishbilarmonlik o'yinlari, taqlid qilish; - darslar, ekskursiyalar; - ijodkorlar va mutaxassislar bilan dars-uchrashuvlar; - ijodiy rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan mashg'ulotlar - ijro darslari, filmlar suratga olish, gazetalarni nashr etish; - video materiallardan foydalanish, Internet, ko'rinish; - "qaror daraxti", "aqliy hujum" usullaridan foydalangan holda murakkab savol va masalalarni yechish. Shuning uchun maktabda o'qitishning innovatsion usullari bolalarda kognitiv qiziqishni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi, o'rganilayotgan materialni tizimlashtirish va umumlashtirishga, muhokama qilish va bahslashishga o'rgatadi. O'zlashtirilgan bilimlarni idrok etish va qayta ishlash orqali o'quvchilar ularni amaliyotda qo'llash ko'nikmalariga ega bo'ladilar, muloqot tajribasiga ega bo'ladilar. Shubhasiz, innovatsion o'qitish usullari an'anaviy usullardan afzalliklarga ega, chunki ular bolaning rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shadi, uni bilish va qaror qabul qilishda mustaqillikka o'rgatadi. o'qituvchi o'quvchilarning jismoniy holatini, ijodkorligini, tez fikrlashlarini hisobga olishi kerak.

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